

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PULAGALA ACHSAH NIRMAL JYOTHI bearing USN 6SU20CS801 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms EAGALA DURGA NANDINI bearing USN 6SU20CS802 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station, Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VENKETESH Rbearing USN 6SU20CS803 has completed his/her internship at Urwa Cyber Police Station ,Mangalore in the first Semester of the Digital and cyber forensic programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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